

1 **Activation of PROCA by HPV16 E7.**

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6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of the protein
9 interacting with cyclin A1 encoded by *Proca* by HPV16 HPV E7.

10 Citations

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